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This book contains all abstracts submitted to the International UFAZ Conference, CPM's 2025 Edition. The abstracts represent cutting-edge research and developments in Chemistry, Process Engineering, and Materials Science. Each abstract has been carefully reviewed by the Scientific Committee and accepted for presentation at the conference. The compilation preserves the original formatting and content of each submission while providing a comprehensive overview of the diverse research topics covered at the conference.

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Abstracts

Analysis of Trap Parameters Associated with Intermediate Luminescence Peaks of Quartz

A. Ahadov^a, S. Mammadov^a, M. Gurbanov^a, A. Abishov^a, A. Ahadova^a

^aInstitute of Radiation Problems, Ministry of Science and Education, Azerbaijan, 9, B. Vahabzade str.

E-mail: a.ahadov@irp.science.az

Abstract

Quartz, a ubiquitous mineral formed across diverse geological environments (igneous, metamorphic, and sedimentary), serves as a critical tool for probing the properties of quartz-bearing materials in geological and mineralogical studies [1][2]. The initial rise (IR) method plays a crucial role in determining the activation energies of electron levels in thermoluminescence (TL) glow curves.

This research focuses on the thermoluminescence parameters associated with intermediate luminescence peaks in quartz. By employing isothermal decay analysis, TL difference curves, and the initial rise method, we aim to identify and characterize the trap structures contributing to the TL signal. The results indicate that the TL glow peaks do not conform strictly to first- or second-order kinetics, suggesting a more complex trapping and recombination mechanism.

TL measurements were performed using a Harshaw 3500 manual reader, where the samples were heated to T_{stop} and held at that temperature for 100 seconds to observe isothermal decay. Initially, the samples were irradiated at ambient temperature with a ^{60}Co source at a dose rate of 1.6 Gy/s, to a dose of 3kGy, followed by heating at 500°C for a duration of two hours. This procedure was repeated three times, with the hypothesis that the deep traps would be filled, thereby preventing them from competing with the intermediate level of traps for free electrons.

Analysis of TL difference curves with different T_{stop} temperatures, obtained by digitally subtracting the residual TL signal, facilitates the identification of three stable T_m stability regions at 145°C, 170°C, and 235°C. The glow curve obtained following isothermal cleaning at ten different temperatures, ranging from 90°C to 170°C, was analyzed to calculate the activation energy using the initial-rise method. The results indicate that the apparent activation energy decreases as the segments of the glow curve are cleaned at increasing T_{stop} temperature.

The study also highlights the impact of deep electron traps and retrapping effects on the determination of activation energy. The findings contribute to a more accurate understanding of TL kinetics in quartz, with implications for dosimetric applications.

Keywords: isothermal decay, quartz, activation energy, frequency factor, thermoluminescence

References

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